

WATER STRESS EVALUATION IN IRRIGATED COTTON USING PROXIMAL INFRARED THERMOMETRY

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Upland cotton requires proper water management to efficiently produce high yields and acceptable fiber quality yet avoid conditions of excess water. Scheduling irrigation using thermally based sensors can overcome limitations other methods of water stress evaluation such as soil water monitoring. The increasing availability of accurate and affordable infrared thermometers (IRTs) that can be integrated into wireless sensor networks has facilitated their use as proximal sensors in irrigation management.

Although a variety of approaches using IRTs have been applied to assess water stress in crops that can be used to schedule irrigation, a crop water stress index (CWSI) based on canopy temperature T_c depression below air temperature T_a (Jackson et al., 1981; Idso et al., 1981; Jackson et al., 1988) may better reflect the degree of water stress because it is closely related to transpiration. The CWSI is calculated as

$$CWSI = \frac{(T_c - T_a) - (T_{cp} - T_a)}{(T_{cx} - T_a) - (T_{cp} - T_a)} \quad (1)$$

where $(T_{cx} - T_a)$ is the canopy temperature depression (or elevation) for a non-transpiring crop and $(T_{cp} - T_a)$ is the canopy temperature depression for a well-watered crop. A theoretical approach can be used to develop the upper and lower baselines by solving the surface energy balance equations. This requires additional meteorological measurements that can also be employed to estimate crop evapotranspiration using the measured canopy temperatures.

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Herein, we examine the use of proximal IRTs for upland cotton located at less than two or three meters above the canopy to assess crop water stress and schedule irrigation. Most of the analysis is synthesized from the recent studies of Schwartz et al. (2024a, 2024b) in the semiarid Texas High Plains. The principal focus in this review was to (i) discuss methodology related to proximal measurements of canopy temperature (2) examine the applicability of theoretically calculated upper and lower temperature depression thresholds across environments, (3) compare soil water based indicators of crop water stress with daily CWSI, and (4) discuss potential difficulties with proximal thermal sensing for implementation under a production environment.

Canopy temperature measurements with stationary, proximal IRT sensors

During the daytime, leaf temperature is dependent to a large extent on the stomatal aperture, transpiration rate, and consequently related to crop water stress. Infrared sensors measure the emittance of radiant thermal energy (E) by a non-blackbody from a surface in accordance with the Stefan-Boltzmann Law:

$$E = \varepsilon\sigma T^4 \quad (2)$$

where T is surface temperature (K), σ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant, and ε is surface emittance. It is obvious that the emitted radiation by a surface is strongly dependent on temperature (to the fourth power). Assuming no dependence on wavelength, acceptable for the range of terrestrial surfaces, the leaf temperature can be evaluated using reference values of emissivity. For cotton leaves, emissivity is approximately 0.97 to 0.98.

Infrared sensors are, by design, sensitive to only the longwave thermal radiation band between ~6 and 14 μm . Infrared sensors are usually calibrated against a black body radiation target over a range of temperatures within a temperature-controlled chamber. Accuracies of $\lesssim 0.5$ °C can be achieved using calibrations. An important design factor of IRTs is the field of view (FOV) which determines how much surface it views at a given distance and tilt angle. Field of views of IRTs used for canopy temperature measurements are usually narrow ($< 23^\circ$) so that the target area can be constrained at greater distances from the canopy. Obtaining an accurate canopy temperature requires that the IRT is oriented appropriately to receive radiation from the desired target area. For a stationary, proximal IRT sensors with a field of view that targets only the crop canopy, the longwave radiation received and consequently the inferred canopy temperature depends on (a) radiation directly emitted by the target

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surface and b) reflected radiation from the background. As the distance between the target and IRT increases, background radiation will increase thereby necessitating corrections to inferred temperature measurement. This is partly why canopy temperature measurements inferred by infrared measurements acquired by unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) may differ from proximal sensors. For proximal IRT sensors, the field of view should target sunlit leaves, avoid soil surfaces, and avoid shadows from the sensor and support mast. Oftentimes sensors are oriented off-nadir in the south and north directions to account for varying leaf angles, solar azimuths and solar altitudes on inferred temperatures. In zones with considerable windspeeds, it is possible for soil to be exposed in the field of view because of plant movement by wind.

Theoretically calculated baselines for upland cotton

Using the meteorological measurements used to estimate reference ET (Allen et al., 1998) and IRT-measured surface temperatures, Schwartz et al., (2024b) calculated the CWSI by solving the energy balance equations with stability corrections (Fig. 1). The lower theoretical threshold was sensitive to the vapor pressure deficit (VPD) with a slope ($-2.20^{\circ}\text{C kPa}^{-1}$) and intercept (2.94°C) and similar to the measured response of Reginato (1982) for Upland cotton in Arizona (Fig. 1). Howell et al. (1984), however, obtained a different slope for Acala cotton in the California Central Coast ($-1.8^{\circ}\text{C kPa}^{-1}$). Based on the work of Schwartz et al. (2024a), canopy temperature response was similar for Upland cotton cultivars with widely varying leaf shape and pubescent characteristics (Fig. 2). The invariance among cultivars and the similar slopes for different regions suggest that the lower baseline presented in Fig. 1 is a good approximation for Upland cotton in the semi-arid and arid US southwest. Because of the relative insensitivity of the upper baseline to the VPD and other meteorological parameters, a constant value of $(T_{\text{cx}} - T_{\text{a}}) = 7.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ may be employed. Consequently, one could use measured air temperature and relative humidity to solve for the CWSI for upland cotton.

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Figure 1. Measured canopy temperature depressions ($T_c - T_a$) and the associated theoretical (Schwartz et al., 2024b) and measured (Reginato, 1982) upper ($T_{cx} - T_a$) and lower ($T_{cp} - T_a$) thresholds for Upland cotton.

Figure 2. Mean 0.25-h canopy temperatures in 2020 for two cultivars two weeks after cutout at the 100% and 33% irrigation level. Shaded areas are the 90% confidence intervals for the FM2334 cultivar using the pooled variance. Ambient air temperature at 2 m is also shown.

Comparison of a soil water based crop water stress with the CWSI

For meaningful irrigation scheduling decisions, the daily integrated CWSI should scale as

$$1 - \text{CWSI} = \frac{ET_c}{K_c ET_o} = K_s \quad (3)$$

where K_c is the calibrated FAO-56 (Allen et al., 1998) crop coefficient, ET_o is the reference ET, and K_s is the crop water stress coefficient for non-standard (water stressed) conditions. Calculated daily CWSI using the theoretically based thresholds

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(Fig. 1) resulted in a linear response ($R^2 = 0.76$) to the stress coefficient K_s (Fig. 3) obtained from the water balance estimation of crop ET (Schwartz et al., 2024ab). Utilizing measured canopy temperatures in conjunction with the surface energy balance equations to infer the diurnal canopy resistance (Fig. 4) permits the calculation of daytime crop ET which compares closely to the soil water balance inferred crop ET provided that the fraction of canopy cover exceeds 0.70 (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Relationship between the daily crop water stress index and the calibrated FAO-56 stress index K_s for the CWSI calculated using the daily average.

Figure 5. Measured and predicted cumulative crop ET determined using measured canopy temperatures to solve for canopy resistance in the surface energy balance for canopy cover fractions greater than 0.7.

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Figure 4. Inferred mean canopy resistance between first square and first white flower

determined using the surface energy balance and measured canopy temperatures.

Limitations and challenges with proximal thermal sensing for irrigation scheduling

Using IRTs for canopy temperature measurements to target scheduling of irrigation is a promising but technically challenging method. An important limitation is that in humid environments or on humid days, low VPD (< 2 kPa) reduces the difference between canopy and air temperatures thereby causing difficulties in assessing water stress. The method is also impractical for use in cotton prior to about first square because of limited canopy cover. Although a two-source energy balance model (Colaizzi et al., 2012) could enable water stress estimation under sparse canopies, its application under a production setting would be challenging.

Scheduling irrigation using canopy temperature measurements can be problematic because CWSI can vary considerably from day to day and using a daily threshold (e.g., 0.2) to trigger irrigations may not perform satisfactorily. Triggering irrigation when the CWSI exceeds a certain time threshold during a single day (O’Shaughnessy et al., 2012) may be more appropriate for managing irrigation. However, because the CWSI does not track readily plant available water in the rooting zone, and because forecasting future canopy temperatures is questionable, it is difficult to infer when the crop will undergo water stress. It is obvious that strategies will need to be evaluated in the field to optimize scheduling strategies. In salt-affect soils, the CWSI can detect stress associated with combined limitations associated with root zone soil water and osmotic

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effects of water uptake by roots, however CWSI thresholds and baselines may differ from those of crops experiencing only water stress. Lastly, for an accurate determination of the CWSI with infrared thermometry, it is necessary to filter out anomalous data caused by sensor faults, obscured or obstructed lenses, and field of views that fail to measure the intended target.

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